

TOBIN TAX AND ITS APPLICABILITY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The talk of a Tobin-type tax keeps surfacing regularly in India as policy makers are concerned about another surge in capital inflows-considering the country's booming GDP growth when the recovery of the world economy remains brittle. The Tobin Tax, named after Nobel Prize-winning US economist James Tobin, was proposed in 1971 for the first time with the intention to levy it on short-term capital currency transactions. At that point of time, the idea was not greeted with zeal, as the 1970s were a period of optimism and confidence in floating exchange rates.

Yet, whenever currency crises have erupted during the past decades, the proposal for a levy on international currency transactions has been debated. The recent turbulence in global financial markets has rekindled interest in the so-called Tobin tax as a tool to discourage speculative currency trading and reduce exchange rate volatility.

The first formal proposal for a tax on spot transactions involving the conversion of one currency into another was made by the US Nobel prize-winning economist, Professor James Tobin, in a lecture at Princeton University in 1972. He further developed the concept in his Presidential Address to the Eastern Economic Association in 1978, which was subsequently published in the Eastern Economic Journal). Since then, the introduction of what has become known as a "Tobin Tax" has at regular intervals figured on the political agenda.

The present paper analysis the Tobin tax and its applicability in India. The paper suggests that there are two key political issues involved in putting such a tax in place. First, it would be necessary to build agreement amongst the major countries to implement a uniform tax, and second, there would have to be agreement on the collection and distribution of the tax revenue. The study tries to find the way ahead regarding Tobin tax.

KEYWORDS: Tobin Tax, foreign currency tax, volatility, cross border currency transactions.

INTRODUCTION

The American economist and Nobel Laureate Prof James Tobin first made the suggestion for a tax on currency transactions to dissuade short term currency speculation in the 1970s. A Tobin tax is defined as a tax on all spot conversions of one currency into another. The tax is intended to put a penalty on short-term financial round-trip excursions into another currency.

It is simple sales tax on currency trades across borders. James Tobin's purpose in developing his idea of a currency transaction tax was to find a way to manage exchange-rate volatility. In his view, "currency exchanges transmit disturbances originating in international financial markets. National economies and national governments are not capable of adjusting to massive movements of funds across the foreign exchanges, without real hardship and without significant sacrifice of the objectives of national economic policy with respect to employment, output, and inflation."

Tobin's more specific concept of a "currency transaction tax" from 1972 lay dormant for more than 20 years but was revived by the advent of the 1997 Asian Financial Crisis. In December, 1997 Ignacio Ramnot, editor of *Le Monde Diplomatique*, renewed the debate around the Tobin tax with an editorial titled "Disarming the Markets". Ramonet proposed to create an association for the introduction of this tax, which was named Association for the Taxation of financial Transactions for the Aid of Citizens. The tax then became an issue of the Global Justice Movement or Alter - Globalization movement and a matter of discussion not only in academic institutions but even in streets and in parliaments in the UK, France, and around the world.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research in common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. One can also define research as a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. The present study has been undertaken to examine the issues to be addressed by means of Tobin Tax.

The present study aims at the following objectives:

- a) To analyze the Tobin tax
- b) To highlight the India's position regarding Tobin tax.
- c) To find the way ahead regarding Tobin tax.

AREA OF STUDY

The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole World. However, opinion of various economists and Professors of Economics and Finance in Jaipur and Moradabad district of Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh respectively, has been taken about the development, barriers and benefits of Tobin Tax. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on Tobin Tax.

We have used qualitative research techniques as focus group discussion with respect to implementation of Tobin Tax. The discussions were based on key initiatives with emphasis on Tobin Tax. The researchers also use the secondary data published in various Business dailies.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Hanke et al. state that “the economic consequences of introducing a [currency-only] Tobin Tax are completely unknown; as such a tax has not been introduced on any real foreign exchange market so far”. At the same time, even in the case of stock transaction taxes, where some empirical evidence is available, researchers warn that “it is hazardous to generalize limited evidence when debating important policy issues such as the transaction taxes”

According to Stephan Schulmeister, Margit Schratzenstaller, and Oliver Picek (2008), from the practical viewpoint it is no longer possible to introduce a non-currency transactions tax (even if foreign exchange transactions were formally exempt) since the advent of currency derivatives and currency exchange traded funds. All of these would have to be taxed together under a “non-currency” financial transactions tax (such as under certain proposals] in the U.S. in 2009 which, although not intending to tax currencies directly, would still do so due to taxation of currency futures and currency exchange traded funds). Because these three groups of instruments are nearly perfect substitutes, if at least one of these groups were to be exempt, it would likely attract most market volume from the taxed alternatives.

According to Stephan Schulmeister, Margit Schratzenstaller, and Oliver Picek (2008), restricting the financial transactions tax to foreign exchange only (as envisaged originally by Tobin) would not be desirable. According to them, a “general FTT seems more attractive than a specific transaction tax” (such as a currency-only Tobin tax), because it could reduce tax avoidance (i.e., substitution of similar untaxed instruments), could significantly increase the tax base and could be implemented more easily on organized exchanges than in a dealership market like the global foreign exchange market.

Most studies of the likely impact of the Tobin tax on financial markets volatility have been theoretical—researches conducted laboratory simulations or constructed economic models. Some of these theoretical studies have concluded that a transaction tax could reduce volatility by crowding out speculators or eliminating individual ‘noise traders’ but that it would not have any impact on volatility in case of sufficiently deep global markets such as those in major currency pairs, unlike in case of less liquid markets, such as those in stocks and (especially) options, where volatility would probably increase with reduced volumes. Behavioural Finance theoretical models, such as those developed by Wei and Kim (1997) or Westerhoff and Dieci (2004) suggest that transaction taxes can reduce volatility, at least in the foreign exchange market. In contrast, some papers find a positive effect of a transaction tax on market volatility. Lanne and Vesala (2006) argue that a transaction tax “is likely to amplify, not dampen, volatility in foreign exchange markets”, because such tax penalizes informed market participants disproportionately more than uninformed ones, leading to volatility increases.

SUPPORT FOR TOBIN TAX

The Tobin Tax has steadily gained support due to the following reasons:

The volume of foreign exchange trading has steadily grown; in fact it has far outstripped the amount necessary to carry out trade. Up to \$2 trillion a day is traded, and only 5% of this is

necessary for financing trade in goods and services. All the rest is speculative activity (in 1975 80% of these transactions were trade-related).

The Tobin Tax has gained credibility as an efficient method of public financing of world development, especially when most developed countries are unable or unwilling to meet their aid promises. According to the OECD, total global aid to developing countries has fallen by about 15% in the last two years alone.

The progressive advance of globalization and the trend towards the deregulation of financial and foreign exchange markets has exacerbated the inherent volatility of these markets. Traders go through session of pessimism and optimism, not necessarily related to economic realities, causing financial markets to swing violently. This constant yo-yoing can have dramatic adverse effects on an economy, particularly on the poor. The result is often unemployment and increases in interest rates, forging the conditions for recession.

ILLUSTRATION OF TOBIN TAX

FIG 1: ILLUSTRATION OF TOBIN TAX

WORKING OF TOBIN TAX

FIG 2: WORKING OF TOBIN TAX

SUPPORT IN SOME G20 NATIONS

The first nation in the G20 group to formally accept the Tobin tax was Canada.

March 23, 1999	The Canadian House of Commons passed a resolution directing the government to enact a tax on financial transactions in concert with the international community.
September, 2009	French President Nicolas Sarkozy brought up the issue of a Tobin tax once again, suggesting it be adopted by the G20.
November, 2009	At the G20 finance ministers' summit in Scotland, the representatives of the Minority Government of Canada spoke publicly on the world stage in opposition to that Canadian House of Commons resolution.
November 7, 2009	Britain Prime Minister Gordon Brown said that G-20 should consider a tax on speculation, although did not specify that it should be on currency trading alone. The BBC reported that there was a negative response to the plan among the G20.
December 11, 2009	European Union leaders expressed broad support for a Tobin tax in a communiqué sent to the IMF.
December 11, 2009	Financial Times reported the following: Since the Nov 7, 2009 summit of the G20 Finance Ministers, the head of the IMF, Mr Strauss-Kahn (now former Head) seems to have softened his doubts, telling the CBI employers' conference: "We have been asked by the G20 to look into financial sector taxes. ... This is an interesting issue. ... We will look at it from various angles and consider all proposals."

For supporters of a Tobin tax, there is a wide range of opinion on who should administer a global Tobin tax and what the revenue should be used for. There are some who think that it should take the form of an insurance: In early November 2009, at the G20 finance ministers summit in Scotland, the British Prime Minister Mr Brown and Nicolas Sarkozy, France's president, suggested that revenues from the Tobin tax could be devoted to the world's fight against climate change, especially in developing countries. They suggested that funding could come from "a global financial transactions tax." However British officials later argued the main point of a financial transactions tax would be provide insurance for the global taxpayer against a future banking crisis."

OBJECTIVE OF IMPOSING TOBIN TAX

The various objectives of imposing Tobin Tax are mentioned herein below:

- a) One argument widely used in favour of the adoption of such a tax is that those who benefit most from globalization should be made to pay for some of the negative effects. In this view, the tax would serve as a mechanism for redistributing resources at international level to benefit those who are excluded from globalization or suffer negative consequences in the form of instability.
- b) The Tobin Tax on short-term cross-border currency transactions is levied to discourage such flows and help stabilize exchange rates by curbing speculation. Since speculative currency trades occur on smaller margins, Tobin Tax reduces or eliminates incentive for speculation. Prof. Tobin argued that national economies and governments are not capable of adjusting to massive movements of funds across borders, without sacrificing the effectiveness of national economic policy with respect to employment, output, and inflation.
- c) His idea was prompted by the collapse of the Bretton Woods system in 1971, which replaced an arrangement of fixed exchange rates ultimately based on the US dollar's peg to gold with a period of volatile floating exchange rates. He wanted to discourage short-term currency speculation, which makes it difficult for countries to implement independent monetary policies by moving money quickly back and forth between countries with different interest rates.
- d) As described by Tobin, the tax involves applying a small charge of as little as or less than 0.1 % on foreign currency transactions to protect countries from exchange-rate volatility caused by short-term currency speculation. The tax on foreign exchange transactions was devised to cushion exchange rate fluctuations. The idea is very simple: at each exchange of a currency into another a small tax would be levied – let's say, 0.1% or 0.2% of the volume of the transaction. This dissuades speculators as many investors invest their money in foreign exchange on a very short-term basis. If this money is suddenly withdrawn, countries have to drastically increase interest rates for their currency to still be attractive. But high interest is often disastrous for a national economy, as the nineties' crises in Mexico, Southeast Asia and Russia have proven.

So, a Tobin tax is expected to realize different objectives:

- a) to reduce exchange-rate volatility by reducing currency speculation;
- b) to raise revenue for international organizations; and
- c) to make national economic policies less vulnerable to external shocks.
- d) The stabilization of exchange rates,
- e) The exploitation of new revenue sources

- f) The redistribution of resources, in particular between financial and producing sectors, and between nations (in particular between the North and the South) , and
- g) Aspects directed toward transforming the world economic order, in particular with the aim of controlling the process of globalization.

EFFECTS OF TOBIN TAX

The effects of Tobin Tax are mentioned herein below:

- a) **FINANCING DEVELOPMENT:** Since the tax could generate significant sums, the idea has attracted the attention of those concerned with financing development. At a national level there are growing fiscal challenges to meet development targets, whilst there is increasing recognition of the need for international cooperation over the critical problems relating to poverty, environment and security. The UN estimates that the cost of wiping out the worst forms of poverty and environmental destruction globally would be around \$225 billion per year.
- b) **REDUCE THE VOLATILITY OF EXCHANGE RATES:** A identical tax on foreign exchange transactions would put off speculation by imposing a small tax on such activity. This would reduce the volatility of exchange rate fluctuations and provide exporters, importers and long-term investors a more stable exchange rate in return for paying the tax.
- c) **REDUCE THE POWER THAT FINANCIAL MARKETS HAVE OVER NATIONAL GOVERNMENTS TO DETERMINE FISCAL AND MONETARY POLICIES:** The tax would give more autonomy to governments to set national fiscal and monetary policies by making possible greater differences between short-term interest rates in different currencies. Such a tax would also reinvigorate the capacity of central banks to alter exchange rate trends by intervening in currency markets. By cutting down on the overall volume of foreign exchange transactions, central banks would not need as much financial clout to intervene.
- d) **RAISE REVENUE:** This tax would yield enormous sums in receipts. Assumptions vary about the actual rate of the tax, the decline in volume of trade, the amount of trade circumventing the tax and transactions which would be exempt. However, just for illustration, assuming a conservative tax rate of 0.2% and an effective tax base of \$75 trillion annually, the tax would yield \$150 billion annually in receipts. Given the declining commitments to bilateral development assistance around the world, the tax could generate important resources to support sustainable human development.

TOBIN TAX AND INDIA

The buzz around a Tobin tax persists in India because the economy faces the clear and present danger of a flood, including the danger of sudden halts of capital inflows. Policy makers, especially those at the central bank, are concerned about the destabilizing consequences of

speculative inflows flooding in and out of the system — which is bound to affect the robust growth dynamic of the Indian economy. Such inflows are typically pro-cyclical, rising in good times and falling in bad times. According to Reserve Bank of India Governor Mr Duvvuri Subbarao, “India has no plans to impose the so- called Tobin tax on foreign capital inflows. He added that the position may be reviewed in future. In his words, “As regards a Tobin type tax, we have not so far imposed nor are we contemplating one. However, it needs reiterating that no policy instrument is clearly off the table and our choice of instruments will be determined by the context.”

Prime Minister Manmohan Singh also ruled out the imposition of a tax on capital flows, referred to as Tobin Tax, saying that portfolio and direct investment into India were manageable. In his words “Tobin Tax has merit in particular situations but as far as India is concerned, we have not reached a stage where capital flows have become a problem. Capital flows into our country both by way of direct investment and by way of portfolio investment have been at reasonable levels. We don’t face situations of the kind which would require an imposition of Tobin Tax”.

In the past, too, Indian authorities have considered the imposition of Tobin Tax but have refrained from moving on it. They have, however, resorted to putting in place checks on inflows through routes such as external commercial borrowings to check a steep appreciation in the value of the rupee. An appreciation in the local currency makes exports less competitive.

To be sure, India’s policy makers are fully aware of the problems in imposing a Tobin-type tax; it can also be evaded through derivatives. It reduces liquidity in the markets. The scope of the tax also needs to be continually widened, resulting in inefficiencies. But it is interesting that even after categorically stating “we have not so far imposed nor are we contemplating one” such a measure, D. Subbarao significantly added that “it needs reiterating that no policy instrument is off the table”! All of this could change in a moment if a tsunami of capital heads India’s way due to shocks in the world of high finance. The upshot is that for all the doubts regarding its efficacy, Tobin's proposal remains very much alive and kicking in the Indian context.

It is also worth noting that Indian fiscal policy also provides for a higher income tax rate on short-term gains (whether or not on the stock exchange) which is not there in Brazil and in most of the countries except Australia, Germany, the US and France.

In view of this, India already has a fiscal environment to protect against short-term volatility. In addition, the implementation of such a tax may also impact genuine hedging transactions which are non-speculative in nature.

A tax on financial transactions will help the developed countries recoup some of the resources spent on bailing out financial concerns. But it will upset the balance of payments stability of countries like India, which depend on capital flows to balance their external account.

The idea of a tax on financial transactions, similar to one imposed by Brazil, has gradually gained currency in international circles. In Brazil's case, this tax, also called Tobin tax, was intended to restrict the flow of volatile capital from the developed world, which had disturbed the stability of its economy.

The IMF viewed this move with displeasure, arguing that it would interfere with the flow of liquidity between markets. The move was, however, considered necessary because the Brazilian currency was appreciating as a result of inflows of capital and Brazil was losing competitiveness in exports as a result.

MERITS OF TOBIN TAX

- a) According to Tobin, the benefits would be reflected in stabilized exchange rates and a consolidation of the autonomy of monetary authorities.
- b) A tax on financial transactions will help the developed countries recoup some of the resources spent on bailing out financial concerns.
- c) The tax can stabilise the global financial markets and also fund specified development projects. After the east-Asian experience, where foreign institutional investors pulled out leading to a crisis, the need for such a tax had been further accentuated.
- d) It will stabilise increasingly volatile currency markets
- e) It will - quite painlessly by the standards of most taxes - raise massive revenue urgently needed for a range of worthy causes

PROBLEMS/DEMERITS OF TOBIN TAX

The Tobin Tax has obvious attractions, but it has a number of disadvantages such as:

One of the major concerns surrounding imposition of a Tobin tax is that if a country were to unilaterally levy such a tax, it would curb capital inflows and hurt its growth prospects, the very reason capital is chasing those countries. An additional fear is that imposition of such a tax by some countries will result in re-routing of capital flows into more lenient jurisdictions or potentially into tax havens making financial transactions even more opaque.

It is not even certain that a Tobin Tax would increase exchange-rate stability. When a currency was under attack by speculators, the cost of the tax would almost certainly already have been discounted, possibly resulting in greater, rather than lower, volatility. A Tobin Tax would have had little effect in preventing the fall of the Mexican peso in early 1995, for instance, not that of the South East Asian currencies in 1997.

It is sometimes argued that measures such as Tobin Tax are not effective over the long run, but may be useful in the context of a crisis. The objective of Tobin Tax is clearly to prevent the eruption of volatility and, therefore, to argue that it should not be taken up before the event is somewhat surprising.

While the rate would be low enough not to have a significant effect on longer term investment where yield is higher, it would cut into the yields of speculators moving massive amounts of currency around the globe as they seek to profit from minute differentials in currency fluctuations.

There would also be considerable problems in defining the tax base and taxable transactions.

The greatest of these is that an effective Tobin Tax needs to be imposed globally: otherwise traders can evade it by shifting their trading to another country.

The Tobin Tax may also reduce market efficiency and liquidity because currency traders make money on very small spreads even tax of a few basis points would drastically reduce volumes.

RELEVANCE OF TOBIN TAX

The global financial crisis reopened the debate on the relevance of Tobin tax. The proponents of the tax argue that ill-effects and risks of volatility are inherent to all financial markets and measures should be in place to curb flows. Many countries such as Brazil, Thailand, Columbia, Chile and Malaysia have similar taxes in place. Economists say globally coordinated action will enhance the effectiveness of the policies at the national level. In 2001, James Tobin said the rate could be close to 0.5%. Economists have proposed financial transaction tax rates ranging between 0.05% and 1%. Even a 0.5% tax applied per transaction in the currency market could discourage trades as the spreads in the many of these transactions are as low as 0.005%.

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

It will be useful to briefly review the experience in regard to such taxes, or measures which have the effect of such a tax. A quick review of the literature available on the subject leads to some very general observations.

Thailand	Experience has not been very positive in terms of realising the objectives. However, it may be argued that adequate determination of public policy to implement measures to curtail inflows including tax was not evident. In any case, the possible volatility in the absence of such measures is difficult to assess.
Columbia	Capital controls reduced external borrowings, but the overall impact is not clear.
Chile	There have been a reduction of short-term flows and some injunction of stability, and to that extent, the taxes may be considered partially effective. However, quasi-fiscal losses, lower investment and growth cannot be ruled out.
Malaysia	The intended results were obtained on all fronts. It is noteworthy that there was a display of determination of public policy in intervention and coordination of several policies.
Brazil	It is still early to draw conclusions, but the tax appears to have achieved some of its intended results, according to the Institute of International Finance.

Both, China and India have taken recourse to several measures which have had the effect of Tobin Tax in some ways. The empirical evidence in terms of stability and longer term growth is noteworthy.

While it is difficult to generalize, cross-country analysis made so far seems to indicate that capital account management, in particular measures like Tobin Tax, has the effect of dampening flows in the short-run. There is some change in the composition of flows towards longer term. The non-financial direct investment is relatively unaffected. The longer term implications on growth are not easy to assess. Often, these measures had been undertaken in the context of a crisis, and it is difficult to judge the position, if these actions had not been taken. In brief, there is no evidence of serious downside risks of capital account management in the event of recourse to Tobin Tax.

FUTURE PROSPECTS OF TOBIN TAX

In principle, a tax on capital flows is intended to curb the high volatility in cross-border capital flows. However, the idea only gained prominence during the Asian crisis when it was believed that sudden large capital outflows from the south-east Asian countries exacerbated their problems. Chile, Colombia, Brazil, and Malaysia have imposed this tax. The idea is being discussed hotly again as Brazil has introduced a 2 per cent tax on foreign portfolio flows (FDI is not covered) to curb the sharp appreciation of its currency (Brazil previously had a smaller tax that excluded stocks but was withdrawn later on when the credit crisis spread globally). UK Prime Minister Gordon Brown has also mooted a tax on financial transactions to create a pool for possible future bank bailouts. While some other European countries have supported introduction of such a tax, the US has opposed and this makes it unlikely that a global agreement on such a tax would be reached anytime soon.

Separately, some countries like UK and France are also debating whether to impose a tax but for a different reason. They are talking of a global tax not to suck out liquidity, but to penalise excessive risk taking by banks.

A tax like Tobin tax is principally akin to the Securities Transaction Tax (STT) currently levied in India. While initially the imposition of the STT was taken very negatively by the market, over time, Indian markets have accepted the imposition and grown manifold. Indeed, in both the cash and derivatives market, turnover growth has continued since the introduction of the STT.

SUGGESTIONS

After going through the above study the researchers present the following suggestions:

- 1) A tax to curb speculation in foreign currency exchange is an innovative and fair proposal that will contribute to restoring democratic control over our national economies. There are two key political issues involved with putting such a tax in place. First, it would be necessary to forge agreement amongst the major countries to implement a uniform tax, and second, there would have to be agreement on the collection and distribution of the tax revenue.

- 2) A review of the existing taxes in some jurisdictions would point to the feasibility of such taxes at the national level. International coordination for levy of such taxes must be pursued vigorously, but national-level initiatives for the Tobin tax as part of measures to achieve financial stability by individual countries also has much to commend for itself. It is undeniable that globally-coordinated action will enhance the effectiveness of policies at the national level.
- 3) International coordination for levy of such taxes must be pursued vigorously, but national level initiatives for Tobin Tax as part of measures to achieve financial stability by individual countries also has much to commend for itself. It is undeniable that globally coordinated action will enhance the effectiveness of policies at national level.

THE WAY AHEAD

The idea of global taxation and regulation should urgently be pursued. Developing an internationally coordinated policy response would be an important step forward, particularly in terms of advances in intergovernmental co-operation, global governance, global and corporate citizenship. Political will is the key to successful adoption. Grassroots support is building to urge decision-makers to look closely at this opportunity.

A Currency Transaction Tax has considerable potential but raises questions, which needs further assessment. These are some of the questions raised:

- a) What exact structure should it take?
- b) Who should be the implementing bodies?
- c) How the tax affects the market efficiency?
- d) What are alternative mechanisms to stabilise markets?
- e) How would the threshold be calculated?
- f) What would be the impacts on markets at national and international level?

CONCLUSION

To conclude, we can say that it cannot be the case that Tobin Tax by itself would be effective, but it has immense potential when the instrument is used along with complementary policies, in particular, counter-cyclical and macro-prudential measures. A review of the existing taxes at the national level in some jurisdictions would point to the feasibility of such taxes at the national level.

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